

Title: On the role of human-robot joint attention for memory imprinting

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INTRODUCTION:

Pay attention! In a pedagogical interaction, a teacher's ability to grab a student's attention quickly can occupy much of their effort. Joint attention is one of the key communicative competencies that allow humans to enculturate other humans into an ongoing society. I have spent the last 5 years implementing robotic biomimetic attention systems toward gaze sharing for human-robot tutoring systems. Key to tutoring interactions is a robot's ability to follow gaze and deictic gesture as well as attempting to direct the gaze of the student over the course of long interactions. In this talk I will summarize my findings and conclusions while offering avenues of research that will help shape the future behavior of robotic tutors.

AIM:

I conduct multi-disciplinary research in cognitive science and artificial intelligence toward shaping AI to become compatible with the natural behavior of humans. My research focus in human-robot interaction aims to discover new ways a robot's actions can assist a human's activities.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

In this experiment, gaze position was measured and human memory was tested by presenting a 45-minute narrative movie to 60 human participants. For one group of participants, an approximately four-foot tall humanoid robotic platform was used to direct the gaze of the participants for the course of the movie. The robot used directing non-verbal gestures like pointing to direct the gaze of the human participant toward spatial locations to ensure they attended to salient or intended events to be memorized. Post-questionnaire tests were conducted to determine imprinting of important narrative events in the shared story. The robotic software architecture used in this study will not be discussed but could be a topic of conversation should those attending like to discuss.

RESULTS:

I will review a number of intriguing results regarding human-robot shared gaze control. In addition, I will discuss results in memory imprinting or the ability of a robot to impact impress

memories on an interaction partner.. I will discuss the findings of the experiment as it relates to the greater study of joint attention and potential paths for future research.

CONCLUSIONS:

There is a lot to explore at the intersection of social gaze control and memory — **a largely unexplored topic that lies where** cognitive science and A.I. meet. A.I. systems typically are designed to detect all things in a single frame, but visual and cognitive attention tell us a different story. In other words, the student participant may be *looking at* something but not *paying attention* to the events in front of them. How will robots and artificially intelligent agents ensure students are actually paying attention?

KEYWORDS:

Joint attention; human-robot interaction; social robotics; tutoring

BIOGRAPHY:

Nick DePalma recently completed his Ph.D. at the Massachusetts Institute of Technology. His dissertation work was in human robot interaction on the topic of inference for shared beliefs toward mutual state sharing. He is a scholar of the phenomena of human joint attention and of state-of-the-art methods in robotics and artificial intelligence. He is presently a cognitive architect for robotics at Futurewei Technologies. He has published numerous papers in interaction, artificial intelligence and developmental science, and has served on program committees of conferences and workshops on the intersection of interaction science and artificial intelligence methods.